

Do board characteristics affect the financial soundness of Islamic banks

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Abstract

This paper was conducted to analyze the impact of the Board of Directors' characteristics on the financial soundness of Islamic banking, using panel data regression. Composed of 67 Islamic banks over 2015-2018 period. The level of Islamic bank soundness is individually employing the Z-score measure Overall, the results of this study indicate that the soundness of Islamic banks is not adversely affected by the appointment of the independent non-executive director and the institutional director. However, the foreign director and the femal director have a positive impact on the financial soundness of banks. While, the Board of Directors' size does not have any significant effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banks. With this study, we hope to provide new insights to the literature review and identify the relationship between the Board of Directors and the financial soundness of Islamic banking. It has been recommended to increase the level of female presence and the foreign on the Board of Directors of Islamic banks.

Keywords

Board of Directors, Corporate Governance, Financial soundness, Gender diversity, Islamic Banking, Shariah compliance.

Introduction

Over last few decades, the rapid growth of Islamic banking has attract much attention in both number and size all over the world due to the rising demand from customers who are motivated to engage with banks that apply shariah rules (Nomran *et al.*, 2018). Ulussever (2018) finds that the financial assets of the Islamic financial sector increased 50% faster than the other banking sector and reached US\$1.7 trillion in 2013. In the same order of ideas, the financial assets of Islamic institutions are expected to achieve US\$6.5 trillion in 2020. The corporate governance structure is mainly supervised by the Board of Directors and the Shariah Board (Khalil and Taktak, 2020). Grassa and Matoussi (2014) show that the Board of Directors and the Shariah Board play an important and vital role in the Islamic banking corporate governance, they are the two most highly complex organs. The Board of Directors is a vital organ related to the direction and the management of the bank and it is composed of sevrel directors (Amine, 2018). This board play the same role as a conventional bank's board. But, the principles of Islamic rules add responsibilities on the the board of Islamic banking (Hakimi *et al.*, 2018). Directors must insure compliance with shariah laws (Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI), 2010; Hakimi *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the Board of Directors is responsible for the role of the shariah corporate governance effeciency and confirms that this framework is compatible with the size of the Islamic financial institution (IFI) (Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB), 2006; AAOIFI, 2010; Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM, 2010). Hakimi *et al.* (2018) predict that the Board of Directors' composition can impact the corporate governance of banks and has a significant effect on its futures. So, it is important to investigate the Board of Directors' characteristics. In this paper, we analyze the impact of the Board of Directors on the financial soundness of Islamic banking during the period 2015-2018. The rest of the study is organized as follows: Section 2 looks at the literature review on the relationship between the Board of Directors' characteristics and the financial soundness. Section 3 encompasses the research methodology and variables description and the results are presented in Sections 4. Section 5 summarizes the main conclusion.

1. Literature review

1.1. Independent non-executive director

According to resource dependency theory, a huge number of independent directors affords better financial skills and performance (Pfeffer, 1972 in Aduda *et al.*, 2013). The independent non-executive director is responsible for ameliorating the performance and the stability of the IFI, and identifying the main risks (BNM, 2015; Buallay, 2019). Various proponents of agency theory propose that having a higher number of independent non-executive directors permits a better activities control and decreases the manager interests (Jensen and Meckling, 1976; Fama and Jensen 1983). In addition, the independent non-executive director aids the Shariah Board to verify the compliance of financial products with shariah laws (Quttainah *et al.*, 2013). Plus, the presence of independent non-executive directors ensures the Board of Directors independence (Ramly *et al.*, 2018). Others studies, in contrast, ignore the positive impact of the independent non-executive directors on the financial soundness of banks. Add to that, independent non-executive director has difficulty to understand his main responsibilities on the bank because of the refusal of executive directors to disclose information and his limited participation in the financial institution's activities (Lassoued, 2018). The Code of Best Practices for IFI corporate governance suggests that 2/9 of the directors should be independent non-executives (Code of Best Practices for CGIFI in Ibrahim *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, Hawkamah (2011) finds that a majority of the directors have to be non-executive and at least 1/3 of them have to be independent. The BNM Guide (2013) indicates that the independent directors number must be less than 1/3 of the Director. We hypothesize that:

H1. The presence of an independent non-executive director has a positive effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

1.2. Foreign director

According to agency theory, the foreign directors can impact the management of the bank and diminish agency problems (Ujunwa, 2012). In addition, the recruitment of foreigners attracts new investors and enhances the banks' performance (Ramly *et al.*, 2018). The corporate governance standards propose foreign directors to insure that the Board of Directors has experience and various skills to perform its roles (BNM, 2013). However, Boussaada (2012) argues that the directors with various nationalities have difficult to manage the risk. Rafindaa *et al.* (2018) say that foreigners are less familiar with accounting rules and management

practices. This hinders the capacity of the directors to have the necessary information and control the bank (Masulis *et al.*, 2012). We suggest the following hypothesis:

H2. The percentage of foreign directors has a positive effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

1.3. Institutional director

Proponents of passivity thesis say that institutional directors penalize long-term investment projects (e.g. research and development investments). Brickley *et al.* (1988) argue that institutional directors are not independent and vote for the managers interest. Porter (1992) adds that institutional shareholders do not have any particlaur information about the firm and have difficulties to analyse the financial institution position. According to activism thesis, institutional directors encourage management to invest in long-term projects in order to increase the firm's performance and enhance productivity (Jensen and Meckling, 1976). Institutional directors have a good knowledge of the sector problems and the expertise with regard to other directors (Hakimi *et al.*, 2018). Plus, institutional directors are more independent to control managers (Jensen, 1993). This decreases risks and financial costs and ameliorates financial performance (Jensen 1993; Hakimi *et al.*,2018). We propose the third hypothesis:

*H3.*The percentage of institutional directors has a negative impact on the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

1.4. Femal director

From early years, Islam was receptive to women in business and finance (Yar and Ahmed, 2020) and today, Malaysia is the best example of how making money has little to do with gender diversity in Islam. Thus, it will be interesting to explore how differently financial soundness of Islamic banks is affected by gender diversity in the Board of Directors compared to that of their conventional homologue. Several studies conducted by Pathan and Faff (2013) and Khan *et al.* (2019), argue that there is a positive and significant relationship between the gender diversity of the Board of Directors towards financial soundness bank. Even, there are some countervailing arguments that cast doubt on the positive impact of presence of female directors on the soundness of Islamic banks. Firstly, on the one hand, many recent studies divulge that women are more risk averse than men (Khan *et al.*, 2019). On the other site, the literature review predicts that religious people are also more risk averse (Miller and Hoffmann, 1995; Osoba, 2003). Additionally, presence of women in the boardroom of Islamic banks can persuade the

management to adopt too conservative strategy, and certainly make the Islamic banks less competitive. This is in line with Adams and Ferriera (2009) study US non-financial firms and indicate that the boards with more female directors supervisor more strongly, which can adversely impact well-governed corporations. Secondly, gender diversity may represent less religiosity of the Islamic banks to the eyes of Muslims with orthodox view of Islam, and this may adversely affect financial soundness of Islamic banks. According to social role theory, Chizema *et al.* (2015) observe that countries with higher levels of religiosity are more likely to have fewer female board appointments. These aspects might hinder equity-holders of Islamic banks to command more female directors. We suggest to test our fourth hypothesis:

H4: The percentage of women on director's board has a positive impact on the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

1.5. Size

According to resource dependency theory, a board with a large number of directors has a diversity of experience and knowledge (Goodstein *et al.*, 1994). Furthermore, a larger board rises supervisory ability, meets the stakeholders needs and makes good decisions (Pfeffer, 1972; Fama and Jensen 1983). Several studies say that the larger Board of Directors is associated with good financial performance and is able to avoid bankruptcy and run the risk (Hakimi *et al.*, 2018; Buallay, 2019). Proponents of the agency theory, in contrast, argue that a high number of directors presents difficulties to coordinate efforts between the board members and raises the problem communication. Plus, the large Board of Directors enhances agency costs and motivates directors to look for their own interests (Lipton and Lorsch, 1992; Jensen, 1993). In addition, the higher number of board members rises the information asymmetry problem which conducts to conflicts of interest and increases agency problems (Prowses 1997). Bukair and Abdul Rahman (2015) and Buallay (2019) predict that the size of the Board of Directors has a negative impact on the financial performance of banks. The BNM (2013) Guide says that the directors number is an important tool determining the board's effectiveness and the suitable size of the Board of Directors is determined by the complexity and size of the IFI's activities. We hypothesize that:

H5. The size of the Board of Directors has a negative effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

2. Methodology

2.1. Sample

Our sample is composed of 67 Islamic banks over the period 2015-2018. We manually collected data from the annual reports of each Islamic banks. The rate of inflation and the gross domestic product are extracted from the World Bank website.

2.2. Variables measurement

According to Khalil and Taktak (2020), we calculate the Z-score as follows: **Z-score** = $(ROA + ka) / \sigma (ROA)$.

Where: ROA = Return on asset; ka = Total equity/Total assets; $\sigma (ROA)$ = Standard deviation of ROA.

We propose the below model to investigate the impact of Board of Directors' characteristics on the financial soundness of Islamic banking:

$$Z\text{-score}_{it} = C + \beta_1 NE_{it} + \beta_2 AE_{it} + \beta_3 AI_{it} + \beta_4 WOM_{it} + \beta_5 TC_{it} + \beta_6 BS_{it} + \beta_7 AGE_{it} + \beta_8 Mod_{it} + \beta_9 SH_{it} + \beta_{10} OIFI_{it} + \beta_{11} GDP_{it} + \beta_{12} INR_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Hence, (**NE**) is a binary variable that is equal to 1 if an independent non-executive director exists and 0 otherwise, (**AI**) measured by the percentage of institutional directors, (**AE**) measured by the percentage of foreign directors, (**FEM**) measured by the percentage of female directors, (**TC**) measured by the number of director.

We introduce 7 control variables in order to improve our results. **BS** is the logarithm of the bank's total assets, **AGE** is the logarithm of the bank's age, **Mod** is a binary variable that is equal to 1 if the bank has a central Shariah Board and 0 otherwise, **SH** is a binary variable that is equal to 1 if the bank apply the shariah law and 0 otherwise, **OIFI** is a binary variable which is equal to 1 if the bank applies the AAOIFI's standards and 0 otherwise, **GDP** is the gross domestic product, **INR** is the inflation rate.

According to Beck and Katz (1995), the model of our study is estimated by using the Panel Corrected Standard Errors method (PCSE). We employ method eliminates heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation errors by having results that are more robust.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 indicates that the average of (AE) variable is 20.604%. The mean for (AI) variable is 6.693%, which varies from 0% to 100%. The Board of Directors is composed approximately by 8 directors, with minimum of 2 and maximum of 21.

For other control variables, the mean for bank size (BS) is 7.190, while its minimum and maximum values are -0.001 and 11.586 respectively. It seems that the (WOM) variable has an average of 2.560. The average of (AGE) variable is 1.455. The mean for (GDP) variable is 3.061, which ranges from -0.568 to 4.383. (INR) variable varies from -26 to 63.300 with an average of 8.080. The mean for (Z-score) variable is 14.480.

Table1. Descriptive statistics

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Median</i>	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>
<i>AE %</i>	20.604	22.843	11.805	0	80
<i>AI %</i>	6.693	19.457	0	0	100
<i>WOM %</i>	2.560	7.041	0	0	33.333
<i>TC</i>	8.559	2.860	9	2	21
<i>BS</i>	7.190	1.593	7.391	0.001	11.586
<i>AGE</i>	1.455	0.558	1.301	0.568	4.383
<i>GDP</i>	3.061	3.581	3.5	-28	13.4
<i>INR</i>	8.080	13.274	2.8	-26	63.3
<i>Z-score</i>	14.480	14.069	10.500	-1.325	92.414

Source : Authors

Table 2 shows that 44.776% of directors are independent non-executive. Plus, 66.417% of Islamic banks are governed by a central Shariah Board and 54.104% of banks belong to countries whose legal framework used shariah rules. We notice that 35.820% of Islamic banking belong to countries which use the AAOIFI standards.

Table 2. Frequency of binary variables

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Mod</i>		<i>SH</i>		<i>OIFI</i>		<i>NE</i>	
	<i>1</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>Frequency %</i>	66.417	33.582	54.104	45.895	35.820	64.179	44.776	55.223

Source : Authors

3.2. Cross-Correlation Matrix and Test Variance Inflation Factor

Cross-Correlation matrix shows that all the coefficients of correlations are less than the limit (0.7) suggested by Kennedy (2008). We see that our independent variables have a variance inflation factor (VIF) value that is less than 10 which is the limit proposed by Kennedy (1998).

Table 3. Pearson's correlation matrix and VIF coefficients

	<i>NE</i>	<i>AE</i>	<i>AI</i>	<i>TC</i>	<i>WO</i> <i>M</i>	<i>BS</i>	<i>AGE</i>	<i>Mod</i>	<i>SH</i>	<i>OIFI</i>	<i>GDP</i>	<i>INR</i>	<i>VIF</i>
<i>NE</i>	1.000												1.5
	0												7
<i>AE</i>	0.054	1.000											1.3
	0	0											5
<i>AI</i>	-	0.080	1.000										1.1
	0.044	3	0										4
	0												
<i>TC</i>	0.123	0.089	0.204	1.000									1.4
	1	6	9	0									7
<i>WO</i>	0.164	-	-	0.004	1.000								1.1
<i>M</i>	4	0.218	0.021	8	0								6
		2	0										
<i>BS</i>	-	-	0.023	-	0.003	1.000							1.1
	0.236	0.235	8	0.032	0	0							8
	2	5		2									
<i>AGE</i>	-	-	-	0.097	0.050	0.245	1.000						1.1
	0.188	0.164	0.055	9	0	9	0						7
	0	1	5										

<i>Mod</i>	0.211	0.212	0.060	-	0.259	-	0.024	1.000					2.7
	3	5	1	0.043	1	5	3	0					3
<i>SH</i>	-	0.170	-	-	-	-	-	0.518	1.000				2.3
	0.119	9	0.026	0.045	0.195	0.094	0.045	4	0				4
	3		1	0	5	8	4						
<i>OIFI</i>	-	0.344	-	0.008	-	-	-	0.531	0.688	1.000			2.6
	0.046	8	0.092	9	0.207	0.131	0.076	2	1	0			9
	7		5		4	4	2						
<i>GDP</i>	0.130	0.104	0.110	0.132	0.162	0.043	0.030	0.231	-	-	1.000		1.3
	7	9	1	6	5	2	0	8	0.118	0.110	0		1
									7	5			
<i>INR</i>	-	-	-	-	-	0.068	0.056	0.209	0.298	0.375	-	1.000	1.5
	0.381	0.013	0.000	0.038	0.061	3	7	8	2	2	0.229	0	2
	6	0	9	3	8						9		

Source : Authors

3.3. Results and Discussion

Table 4 indicates that the coefficient on *NE* is negative and significant ($p\text{-value} < 0.1$). H1, therefore, is not supported. This means that the independent non-executive directors has a negative and significant impact on the financial soundness of Islamic banks. This result does not confirm the study of Lassoued (2018) and Buallay (2019) and supports rooting theory suggesting that managers use strategies which make the role of directors passive. Managers nominate unqualified independent directors in order to poor the role of the Board of Directors. Furthermore, this finding confirms the results of several studies (Amine, 2018; Hakimi *et al.*, 2018; Mansoor *et al.*, 2019), the resource dependency theory and the agency theory, and indicates that the independent non-executive director is not able to manage the Islamic banking. In addition, Table 4 shows that the coefficient associated with (*AE*) variable has a significant and positive impact on the financial soundness of Islamic banking. H2, thus, is supported. This result confirms agency theory and suggestions of previous researches (Ramly *et al.*, 2018; Mansoor *et al.*, 2019). The coefficient on *AI* does not have any significant effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banking. H3, therefore is not confirmed. This result does not

support passivity thesis and activism thesis, and contradicts the research of Hakimi *et al.* (2018). The coefficient associated with (WOM) variable has a significant and positive effect on the financial soundness of banks. H4, thus, is supported. This means that the femal directors have a positive impact on the financial soundness. This result strengthens the studies conducted by Pathan and Faff (2013) and Khan *et al.* (2019). Table 4 indicates that (TC) variable does not have any significant effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banking. So, H5 is not confirmed. This result does not support suggestions of resource dependency theory and proponents of agency theory, and contradicts the findings of previous researchers (Amine, 2018; Buallay, 2019). We notice that the control variables of this study (BS, AGE, Mod, SH, OIFI, INR, GDP) does not have any significant effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banking .

Table 4. Regression Results

<i>Independent Variables</i>	<i>Coef.</i>	<i>Z</i>	<i>P> z </i>
<i>BS</i>	-0.517	-1.42	0.155
<i>AGE</i>	0.583	0.43	0.668
<i>Mod</i>	-0.196	-0.06	0.955
<i>SH</i>	-0.599	-0.17	0.864
<i>OIFI</i>	-2.334	-0.75	0.452
<i>GDP</i>	-0.021	-0.15	0.878
<i>INR</i>	0.022	0.32	0.752
<i>TC</i>	0.369	1.27	0.205
<i>NE</i>	-6.485	-3.78	0.000***
<i>AE</i>	0.091	1.81	0.070*
<i>AI</i>	-0.040	-0.51	0.612
<i>WOM</i>	0.309	2.22	0.027**
<i>Cons</i>	16.281	3.71	0.000***
<i>R²</i>		32.68%	
<i>N</i>		268	

Notes : *significant at 10 per cent; ** significant at 5 per cent and *** significant at 1 per cent

Source : Authors

Conclusion

This research investigates whether and how differently financial soundness of Islamic banks is affected by the Board of Directors' characteristics. To response this question, we study a unique sample of 268 observations on Islamic banks in 2015-2018 period. We employ the PCSE method in order to avoid auto correlation and heteroscedasticity problems. The results show that the independent non-executive director has a negative effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banking. However, the foreign director and the femal director have a positive impact on the financial soundness of banks. Hence, the policy makers need to make certain reforms so that the foreign director and the proportion of female directos in case of Islamic banks should be increased to cover the gap of gender diversity. Plus, we notice that there is no significant relationship between the institutional director, the Board of Directors' size and the financial soundness of Islamic banks. This study offers a useful proof for academics, regulators, banking associations, etc. and gives a great contribution to the literature review on the study of the corporate governance and their effect on the financial soundness of Islamic banks. The results have implications for including in the future research paper other corporate governance structures in order to better assess the relationship between the corporate governance mechanisms and the financial soundness of Islamic banks.

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